

Empowered Queens and Wealthy Empresses: Unraveling the Role of Mughal Women in Controlling Trade-Generated Wealth in Mughal India

Rohan Mathur¹

The Heritage Xperiential Learning School, Gurugram, Haryana, India

ABSTRACT:

The role of Mughal women in medieval India extends far beyond traditional perceptions, encompassing significant influence over trade and economic wealth. This paper aims to investigate the pivotal roles that Mughal queens and empresses played in shaping and controlling trade networks and managing the empire's wealth during the 16th and 17th centuries. Understanding these roles is crucial for a comprehensive view of Mughal economic history, as it reveals how influential women contributed to the empire's prosperity and stability in a patriarchal society. Through a detailed review of existing scholarship, this research essay highlights the contributions of Mughal women to economic policies, trade practices, and wealth accumulation, challenging conventional narratives that focus mainly on male figures. The findings demonstrate that Mughal women were not only passive figures but active participants in economic and political spheres, wielding substantial control over trade and wealth. This research contributes to a more nuanced understanding of Mughal history and the complex roles of its female figures.

Key Terms: Mughal history, Mughal women, Mughal economy.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The contributions of Mughal queens and princesses have often been overshadowed by the prominence of Mughal emperors, even though they played vital roles in the social and political life of the Mughal Empire, leaving enduring legacies in art, architecture, literature, and governance. Aristocratic Mughal women were actively involved in politics and society, enriching the diverse culture of the Mughal era. Studying how Muslim women were treated in Mughal India 400 years ago is important because key figures like Aisan Daulat Begum, Gulbadan Banu Begum, Nur Jahan, Mumtaz Mahal, and Jahanara Begum had a significant impact on the empire's growth and success. This study also allows for meaningful comparisons between the social, political, and economic status of women then and now. These women were influential in both the harem and the court, advising the emperor and engaging in politics. The 'zenana,' often misunderstood as merely a place of pleasure, was a multicultural space where powerful women from various backgrounds held advisory roles and

led privileged lives. Despite their political and economic importance, detailed records of these royal women, who defied gender roles imposed by societal norms, are rare. (Arora, 2023)

In Mughal India, women's labor was primarily unpaid and integrated into family income controlled by men. Their roles in agriculture included weeding, transplanting, picking saffron flowers (in Kashmir), husking and grinding grain, caring for cattle, and engaging in textile crafts like ginning cotton and spinning yarn. Women assisted artisanal men in various household tasks, such as preparing clay while men potters worked on the wheel. The gender-based division of labor was prevalent, even within the same occupation (e.g., women were spinners, men were weavers; men were bricklayers, women were brick carriers). This refers to the quintessential traditional gender-based division of labor. In that era, child marriage and polygamy were prevalent among the nobility. Nowadays, women have different social and political rights like the right to vote. One-third of the Members of Parliament seats must be reserved for women. There was little competition between genders for the same jobs, with distinct roles assigned based on gender. In domestic service, male and female slaves further complicated the wage market, introducing additional factors not present in non-domestic work environments. Household management and chores were primarily the domain of women across all classes. Wealthier households employed female servants to alleviate women's workload. Female servants were extensively involved in household tasks, including grinding, cleaning, fetching water, and agricultural work. Concubinage was a prominent institution in royal households, with concubines overseen by matrons and eunuchs. Midwifery and wet-nursing were essential roles for women, particularly in elite families. European travelers such as François Bernier (French) and William Hawkes (British) provided detailed descriptions of women's socio-cultural aspects and status during the Mughal period (Sinha, 2020). Contemporary sources offer limited information on women's professions, necessitating the use of European travelogs to complement existing knowledge. Women in Mughal India can broadly be categorized into royal women and commoners, with differing levels of privilege and opportunities. Women actively participated in agricultural activities, including farming, rice beating, and grain grinding (Guchhait and Kaur, 2023). Some women, especially from ruling and noble families, engaged in commercial activities, including overseas trade and commerce. Royal women like Maryam Zamani and Nur Jahan were notable figures in trade and commerce, owning ships and engaging in profitable ventures. Despite social customs and male prejudices, royal women had more privileged positions and opportunities for education and business ventures compared to common women. (ToI, 2024). European travelers' accounts provide valuable insights into the social and cultural lives of women, especially commoners, during the Mughal period.

Certain works have led to increased interest in the subject. Distinguished scholar Suraiya Farooqi focuses on the interaction between elites and societies from the early 16th to mid-18th centuries, excluding the complex Safavid world (Guchhait, S. and Kaur, D., 2023). The Mughal Empire's economy was based on agriculture and trade, with exports like rice, textiles, tobacco, and metals, and imports such as spices, sugar, oil, horses, and textiles from Asia and Europe. Muslim merchants brought gunpowder, paper, and Chinese porcelain to Mughal India, trading spices, cotton cloth, indigo, and other goods. The Mughal Empire was often viewed through the lens of their emperors and men, but women were equally important. Today, women are still denied many rights in different countries and regions (EnrouteI, 2024). This paper will explore some of the more prominent Mughal women, including empresses, whose lives and roles have found mention only in the sidelines of the predominantly male-centered depiction of Mughal history.

1. Gulbadan Begum (1523-1603)

Gulbadan Begum, a prominent figure among Mughal royal women, played a significant role in the empire's economic endeavors through various means. This is evident in her support for traders and craftspeople, which significantly boosted trade. She oversaw agricultural productivity, collected taxes, and guaranteed the financial stability of tenants and employees while serving as a member of the royal dynasty. (BBC, 2024). This administration was essential to keeping her estates financially stable in addition to giving her a source of income. Her charitable endeavors were remarkable; she gave to the underprivileged, paid for the building of public infrastructure like wells and serais, and assisted religious and educational establishments (Liddle, M. 2024). These initiatives had a significant impact on the economy because they provided the necessary resources and infrastructure to reduce poverty and boost local economies.

In addition, Gulbadan Begum supported poets, painters, and craftsmen, greatly enhancing the Mughal court's cultural and economic life. An important component of the Mughal economy, the flourishing arts and crafts sector was made possible by this assistance. Her sponsorship fostered the growth of several crafts, which in turn helped many artists find employment and added to the empire's general prosperity (Lal, R. 2024). Gulbadan Begum was an aging stateswoman with significant power in the royal court who probably advised on economic policy as well. She even penned the biography of King Humayun, 'Humayunama.' (Sasidharan, D. 2024.)

To sum up, Gulbadan Begum's diverse contributions to the Mughal Empire's humanitarian endeavors, land management, economic operations, support for the arts, and advising function

highlight the crucial role that royal women played in the Mughal Empire's cultural and economic development. Her engagement in these domains underscores the noteworthy power that royal ladies possess in the wider socio-economic sphere, guaranteeing that their sway beyond the boundaries of the harem reaches the core of the empire's economic and cultural activities (Malhotra, S. 2018.)

Image 1: A Portrait of Gulbadan Begum

Source: (Malhotra, S. 2018.)

2. Hamida Banu Begum (1527-1604)

Hamida Banu Begum, the wife of Emperor Humayun and mother of Emperor Akbar, was a significant figure in Mughal history. Born to the respected family teacher of the Hindal family, Sheikh Ali Akbar Jami, a Persian Shia Muslim and a Sufi spiritualist, Hamida was known for her beauty and poise from a young age. She had always had a love for reading and had many books like the Ramayana, the Divan-i-Hijri (a book of poems written by Khvajah Hijri) (Storytrails, 2022). At the age of 14, she captivated Humayun during a gathering, prompting him to immediately request his stepmother Dildar Begum to arrange their marriage. The proposal was made during a turbulent period when Humayun was escaping Sher Shah's army and had just lost his crown (ThePrint. 2019). It was Humayun's propensity to want to grow his harem, even in spite of his vulnerable condition. Humayun regained his throne in Delhi in 1555 and hence became emperor again. Hamida's joy was short-lived, too, since Humayun passed away tragically less than a year later after tumbling down the stairs of his Purana Quila library. Hamida lived for over five more decades after her loss, during which time she was quite influential in Mughal politics (Lab, T.H. 2019). Humayun fulfilled a significant religious obligation when she traveled to Mecca with her stepsister, Gulbadan Begum, on the holy Muslim pilgrimage.

Hamida Banu Begum made significant political interventions in her role as Queen Mother. She supported and advised her son Akbar throughout his early reign, especially because he was a young and inexperienced leader. Her influence was felt when Akbar removed Bairam Khan as his regent

and again when she supported her grandson Jahangir. Throughout her life, Akbar treated his mother with the utmost respect and dignity, as he regarded her in the highest regard. Hamida Banu Begum was buried in Humayun's Tomb upon her passing in 1604, which bears witness to her lasting influence and the important part she played in the Mughal Empire. Her life narrative demonstrates her tenacity, her religiosity, and the great regard she enjoyed among the royal family (The Asian Age).

Image 2: A Portrait of Hamida Banu Begum

Source: (The Asian Age)

3. **Mariam Uz-Zamani (1544-1623)**

Emperor Akbar's wife and Emperor Jahangir's queen mother, Mariam-uz-Zamani, was important to the Mughal Empire's economic activity. As part of a political arrangement, Mariam-uz-Zamani, a Rajput princess by birth, wed Akbar and went on to become the longest-serving Hindu queen of the Mughal Empire (ToI). She was renowned for her grace, elegance, intelligence, and power in the legal system. Her legacy within the Mughal empire was further cemented when she gave birth to Jahangir, the eldest surviving son and successor of Emperor Akbar, and also served as Shah Jahan's grandmother (Anon, n.d.).

She was deeply involved in the export of items including cotton, indigo, silks, leather, metal, carpets, opium, and gems as the owner of the magnificent ship called Rahimi. In addition to being a trade ship, the Rahimi also transported pilgrims to Mecca for the Hajj. The ship's conclusion was ultimately caused by its bad reputation, which reached Europe (Aggarwal, 2023). With a personal stake in the Bayana indigo plantation, Mariam-uz-Zamani even provided funding for the building of a stepwell to supply water to the plants. Her mission was to gather the indigo and ship it to Mocha, which is close to Mecca. She felt severely humiliated when Hawkins's representative outbid her for the entire harvest. After lodging a complaint with Emperor Jahangir, Hawkins left Agra in 1611 (Kapadia, n.d.).

The Rahimi was seized by the Portuguese navy in 1613, and its cargo and occupants were transported to Goa. Jahangir was enraged by this behavior, which was directed as a serious insult to the Mughal Empire. Jahangir urged the Portuguese to hand over the ship, but they refused, underestimating Jahangir's determination (Findly, 1988).

Image 3: A Portrait of Mariam Uz-Zamani

Source: (India Today, n.d.)

4. Ruqaiya Begum (1557-1626)

Ruqaiya Begum, a distinguished Mughal princess (Shahzadi), was the only daughter of Mughal prince Hindal Mirza, who was Emperor Akbar's youngest paternal uncle. Her lineage made her the granddaughter of Babur, the founder and first emperor of the Mughal Empire, and the niece of Humayun, the second Mughal emperor. Ruqaiya's remarkable ancestry placed her in the center of the early Mughal dynasty's history. Ruqaiya, the main consort and first wife of Akbar, was an important figure in the Mughal court (pantheon.world, n.d.). Besides being a union of two people, her marriage to Akbar established a political coalition that strengthened Akbar's influence. She had a significant role in running the Mughal harem, which was called an excellent political sense and a solid understanding of courtly matters.

Ruqaiya was more than a consort; she had other powers as well. Early in the 1600s, tensions arose between Akbar and his son Jahangir. Ruqaiya's diplomatic qualities were essential in organizing a reconciliation. Her actions were crucial in facilitating the orderly transfer of power that led to Jahangir's ultimate appointment to the throne (The Heritage Lab, n.d.). Through her act of mediation, she not only proved her devotion to her husband but also her political knowledge, influence, and expertise. Ruqaiya was renowned for her strong character and sharp mind throughout her life.

A Portrait of Ruqaiya Begum

Source: (The Heritage Lab, n.d.)

5. Maham Anga (unknown-1562)

Maham Anga, the wet nurse and foster mother of Emperor Akbar of the Mughal Empire, was deeply loved and respected by him, eventually becoming his political advisor. During Akbar's teenage years, she briefly acted as regent. When Akbar ascended the throne at thirteen, Bairam Khan served as regent but faced much criticism, including from Maham Anga (WISE Muslim Women, 2010). Anga and her son Adham convinced Akbar to send Khan on a Hajj to Mecca. Dissatisfied, Anga urged Akbar to have Khan executed, but an Afghan carried out the act.

With Khan removed, Anga assumed his role, increasing her power during a period known as the "Petticoat Regency," where she and her supporters manipulated Akbar as a puppet ruler (nadeemrezavi, 2021). The period between 1560 and 1564 A.D. is sometimes referred to as the era of "petticoat government" by some historians. They believe that during this time, Akbar was under the influence of the ladies of the harem. Adham caught hoarding loot, returned most of it but kept two women (Ghosh, 2021). To prevent them from revealing his deceit, Anga had the women killed. Anga died shortly after Adham's violent execution by Akbar for murdering the emperor's favorite general. Some accounts claim Akbar personally threw Anga from the roof upon discovering her conspiracy. Maham Anga also patronized the construction of Khair-ul-Manzil, a mosque near the Old Fort in Delhi, which later served as a madrasa (thewire.in, n.d.).

Maham Anga (Akbar's Foster Mother)

Source: (India Today, 2024)

6. Nur Jahan (1577-1645)

One of the most influential women in 17th-century India was Empress Nur Jahan. Born Mihr un-Nisa, she was later named Nur Jahan (light of the world) by her husband, Mughal Emperor Jahangir. She ruled over a region much more diverse than that of Queen Elizabeth I, her contemporary. Under her leadership, the Mughals dominated a large portion of the Indian subcontinent for over 300 years, creating one of the largest and most powerful kingdoms in India. Nur Jahan's story is one of ambition, power, and resilience.

Nur Jahan's life was marked by exceptional circumstances. She wed Jahangir, the most powerful man in India, at a time of tremendous diversity and global impact. As the Mughal empress, Nur Jahan was very important and had a close relationship with her husband. After their 1611 marriage, Jahan soon regarded Jahangir's favorite and final bride (Schuster, 2017). Through Jahangir's weakness to alcohol and drugs, Jahan slowly began to take on a role other than 'royal wife'. Jahangir relied on Jahan to support him in ruling and to keep him well. Nur Jahan, a well-known figure in the seventeenth-century Mughal Empire, left a lasting legacy through her numerous accomplishments and her knowledge of a wide range of subjects, including politics, economics, music, and the arts (Agrawal, 2018). Nur Jahan's sharp wit, education, and political acumen made her a formidable figure in the Mughal court. She actively engaged in state affairs, contributing to decision-making processes and shaping the course of governance (Bajaj, 2018).

Nur Jahan improved agriculture, constructed better roads, and aided in Imperial trade. She oversaw the tax collection from European trade and was heavily involved in the empire's management. Her effective management of commercial matters demonstrated both her administrative and collaboration skills with many nationS (Khan, 1990). In addition to her financial responsibilities, Nur Jahan was a

skilled diplomat who worked with strong women from many countries. This intellectual and cultural exchange not only improved her understanding of the world but also strengthened the connections that bound the Mughal Empire to other nations (Factinate, n.d.). The commissioning of the building of serais involved the active participation of royal women. Serais were substantial rest areas and inns that provided food, lodging, and shelter to travelers along roadways. Jean-Baptiste Tavernier, Peter Mundy, and Rudyard Kipling frequently mention the serais scattered throughout the Mughal empire in their travelogs and stories. In his book "Storio do Mogor" or "Mughal India," Niccolao Manucci describes sarais as medieval melting pots, where traders, craftsmen, adventurers, and occasionally thieves and conmen converged, offering various employment opportunities for citizens. She was an important empress in maintaining trade relations with Europe and other evolving civilizations. Nur Jahan oversaw the construction of infrastructure like roads and bridges, facilitating easier travel and trade of goods.

She was gifted in the arts, literature, and religion in addition to politics and economics. She made significant contributions to Indian culture via her compassionate endeavors, jewelry design, textile design, and poetry. India's Mughal history is still shaped today by the legacy of Nur Jahan. She was the only Mughal empress, notably, to have coins minted in her honor. Nur Jahan supported the arts in addition to having an impact on the economy. These monuments, which stand apart for their great design and elegance, are evidence of her love of art and culture. Nur Jahan's primary focus was to grow the textile and design industries in Mughal India. Her unique approach to jewelry, carpets, and clothing enhanced the work and encouraged artisans to push the boundaries of their abilities. Nur Jahan raised the worth of Persian art and culture at the Mughal court by popularizing it and drawing influence. In Lahore, Pakistan, on December 17, 1645, she passed away at the age of 68. Her importance is still being emphasized centuries after her death, and her legacy will live on (Google Arts & Culture, n.d.).

Nur Jahan - One of the most influential Princesses in the Mughal Era.

Source: (Jabr, 2021)

7. Mumtaz Mahal (1593-1631)

Mumtaz Mahal was the loyal companion of Shah Jahan. Shah Jahan showed how much he trusted her by giving her his imperial seal, the Muhr Uzah, which demonstrated how close they were. Mumtaz Mahal, who is frequently presented as the ideal wife, was committed to helping Shah Jahan and their family and did not pursue political power, serving as an example of committed marriage and love. She had great authority even though she had no desire to hold political office; Shah Jahan often sought her advice on matters of state (Factinate, n.d.). Their bond emphasizes how important a trusted ally and advisor she is, giving her great political power. During the period when the Deccan kingdoms of Bijapur and Golconda were conquered in 1686–87, resulting in a prolonged economic crisis and warfare with the Marathas, her support and counsel were invaluable to Shah Jahan (Taj Mahal, n.d.).

With fourteen children, Mumtaz Mahal was an empress and a mother figure of great importance. While accompanied by Shah Jahan on a military mission at Burhanpur in 1631, she passed away during delivery. Shah Jahan was deeply affected by her death, withdrawing from public life for a year in mourning. The Taj Mahal in Agra, a beautiful monument that took over 22 years to build and serves as a symbol of their eternal love, was built as a result of their tremendous sadness (Lal, 2013). The Mughal court chroniclers recorded Mumtaz Mahal's demise and Shah Jahan's intense grief, noting that the emperor gave up luxury and entered a state of profound sadness as a result of her death (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2010).

Her reputation and the long love she shared with Shah Jahan were cemented when her bones, first buried in Burhanpur, were subsequently transported to Agra to lie in the Taj Mahal. In addition to being a work of architectural art, the Taj Mahal is still a reminder of Mumtaz Mahal's life and their unwavering love (Zeidan, 2019). This also proves the point that royal Mughal women were a huge source of support for their husbands. They bore their children while they were out fighting battles, took care of the palace, and always kept the family together.

Mumtaz Mahal: The wife of Shah Jahan

Source: (Britannica, 2019)

8. Jahanara Begum (1614-1681)

Princess Jahanara Begum (1614-1681) was a remarkable figure among Mughal women, known for her involvement in both domestic and overseas trade, which was a rarity during her time. With an annual income of three million rupees, she also derived revenue from her port in Surat, allocated for her betel expenses. Additionally, she owned two ships, the Sahibi and the Ganjavar, which transported goods produced at her factories and engaged in trade with the English and Dutch. Records from 1643 show that one of her ships carried pilgrims and merchandise valued between 5,000 and 10,000 rupees. Jahanara took an active role in hiring captains and crews for her vessels, demonstrating her hands-on approach to maritime commerce (Ganeriwal, 2020).

As Shah Jahan's daughter, Jahanara dedicated her entire life to her father. Known for her wit, sharp intellect, caring nature, and courage, her life changed dramatically after the untimely demise of her mother. Despite Shah Jahan having other wives, he awarded Jahanara the title of First Lady (the Padishah Begum). In his deep mourning, Shah Jahan found solace in her company, entrusting her with royal duties and power uncommon for princesses of that era. She was even allowed to live outside the Agra Fort in her palace. Half of her mother's wealth was given to her, with the remaining half divided among her siblings (Mughallibrary.com, 2015). From being a carefree girl, Jahanara was thrust into state politics and tasked with resolving family matters. A curious learner, she was a follower of the Sufi saint Mullah Shah Badakshi, who taught her about the Sufi order. Her life took a perilous turn when she was injured in a fire, but she was successfully treated by a mendicant. Upon her recovery, while Shah Jahan distributed coins and rubies among the public, Jahanara paid a visit to Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti's shrine in Ajmer.

Jahanara contributed significantly to architecture and religious development. She designed Chandni Chowk in Shahjahanabad, the capital at the time, and facilitated trade with Dutch merchants,

enhancing the city's influence. Jahanara not only made significant contributions to architecture but also had a ship that she used to trade with Dutch and English businessmen. She made a big contribution to helping the poor in Mecca and Medina and financing mosques. Her dedication to assisting others was demonstrated by her philanthropic contributions and support of beneficial initiatives.

Jahanara was very close to Shah Jahan's chosen crown prince, Dara Shikoh. On the other hand, Roshanara, her younger sister, had a bitter attitude towards her. Jahanara was a devout woman who was committed to her father and the kingdom, in contrast to Roshanara, who supported the misuse of authority and the amassing of money. She didn't think twice to express her disapproval of Roshanara and Aurangzeb's prejudice against minorities and their father. Jahanara died peacefully in 1681 at the age of 67 and was buried according to her wishes in a tomb in the Nizamuddin Dargah in New Delhi. Her gravestone inscription reads,

“He is the living, the sustaining
Let no one cover my grave except greenery,
For this very grass suffices as a tomb cover for the poor
The annihilated Fakira Lady
Jahanara Daughter of Shah Jahan the Warrior.” (Google Arts & Culture, n.d.)

Jahanara Begum - The Daughter of Shah Jahan

Source: (India Today, 2024)

9. Roshanara Begum (1617-1671)

Roshanara Begum, the daughter of Shah Jahan and Mumtaz Mahal, held considerable sway over her brother Aurangzeb, acting as his trusted advisor during his rule. Her influence reached beyond the royal court, as she played a key role in enriching Mughal culture by supporting the arts, literature, and architecture (Desk & News, 2024). One notable example of her patronage is Roshanara Bagh in

Delhi, a garden complex she commissioned as a personal retreat. In the serene surroundings of this garden, she indulged in her passions for poetry, gardening, and spirituality, away from the hinges of court life (The Womb, 2020).

On the other hand, her sister Jahanara Begum also held substantial power and influence. Upon the return to normalcy, Shah Jahan appointed Jahanara as the Padshah Begum, a role that was not merely honorary but held significant authority. She could independently pass orders, make recommendations to the emperor, and perform certain actions in his absence. Shah Jahan entrusted her with more than half of Mumtaz Mahal's estate, showcasing his confidence in her capabilities. Jahanara proved to be a successful entrepreneur, notably earning profits through a ship she owned in Surat. She utilized her wealth for famine relief, pilgrimages, almsgiving, and sponsoring mosques, as well as overseeing the development of Chandni Chowk. Additionally, Jahanara was an accomplished writer, penning a respected biography of the Sufi saint Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti (Akhtar, 2023).

A Portrait of Roshanara Begum

Source: (India Today, 2024)

10. Zeb-un-Nissa (1638-1702)

Zeb-un-Nissa, born to Emperor Aurangzeb and Empress Dilras Banu Begum, received an extensive education in languages, literature, and sciences, reflecting her privileged upbringing. Her intellectual growth was significantly shaped by notable mentors such as Mir Taqi Mir, a renowned Urdu and Persian poet, and Sa'idullah Khan Dehlvi 'Husaini', who guided her in Persian literature and poetry. Additionally, Muhammad Ibrahim 'Zauq' influenced her poetic style, while her close friend and fellow poet, Bibi Gulsukh, supported her intellectual pursuits (Sharma, 2023). The Sufi scholars introduced her to the profound philosophies of Sufism, which had a lasting impact on her worldview

and writings. Royal courtiers and scholars further enriched her intellectual development through engaging in discussions and debates.

Adopting the pseudonym "Makhfi," meaning "Hidden One," Zeb-un-Nissa explored themes in her poetry with remarkable freedom, unburdened by societal and courtly constraints. Her poetry delved into various themes, including love and longing, both earthly and divine, as well as spirituality and mysticism. Her works, deeply rooted in Sufi philosophy, often discussed the soul's journey and union with the divine. She also addressed the complexities of human experience, touching on themes of joy, sorrow, empowerment, and identity, reflecting her unique position as a princess in a patriarchal society (De, 2020).

Zeb-un-Nissa's use of nature as a metaphor for change and interconnectedness, along with her introspective and self-exploratory themes, added depth to her writings. She often wrote about suffering and resilience, emphasizing the strength found in adversity, and highlighted the universal nature of human emotions, advocating for unity and universality. The pseudonym "Makhfi" was significant as it allowed her to express herself openly in the conservative Mughal court, challenging gender norms and navigating royal constraints. It connected her to a tradition of pseudonymous writing in Persian and Urdu literature, allowing her artistic endeavors to flourish without being overshadowed by her royal identity (Sundus, 2018). Her influence on literature and culture is profound, with her poetry continuing to inspire and resonate with readers. Her works are celebrated for their depth and authenticity, providing a unique voice in the world of literature and poetry. Zeb-un-Nissa's enduring literary legacy highlights the power of poetic expression, making her a significant figure in Persian and Urdu literature.

Zeb-un-Nissa's intellectual journey and her contributions to literature have left an indelible mark on the cultural landscape. Her ability to blend personal introspection with universal themes has made her poetry timeless. As a patron of the arts, she not only created a rich body of work but also fostered an environment where artistic and intellectual pursuits could thrive. Her legacy is a testament to the enduring power of the written word and its ability to transcend time and societal constraints (Sundus, 2018). Today, Zeb-un-Nissa is remembered as a pioneering female poet whose work continues to be studied and admired for its emotional depth, spiritual insight, and lyrical beauty. Her contributions to the Mughal cultural heritage remain a source of inspiration for poets and scholars alike, ensuring that her voice continues to be heard through the ages.

A portrait of Zeb-Un-Nissa

Source: (India Today, 2024)

2. DISCUSSION:

Ira Mukhoti once remarked, "indeed, the Mughal women will be better educated than most of their contemporaries around the world." The queens and princesses of the Mughal Empire were instrumental in its socio-economic and cultural development. These women, far from being mere ornaments of the royal court, played pivotal roles in various spheres of the empire's functioning. Influential figures such as Gulbadan Begum, Hamida Banu Begum, Maryam Zamani, Ruqaiya Begum, Maham Anga, Nur Jahan, Mumtaz Mahal, and Jahanara Begum were deeply involved in administration, trade, and cultural patronage. Their contributions spanned politics, economics, and the arts, highlighting their significant and multifaceted influence on the empire (Mukhtoy, 2018).

Gulbadan Begum, for instance, provided invaluable insights into the royal household through her writings, offering a rare female perspective on the historical events of her time. Hamida Banu Begum's influence on her son Akbar's upbringing and governance underscores the significant impact royal women had on policy and leadership. Maryam Zamani's involvement in commercial ventures illustrates how women could significantly impact economic activities, while Ruqaiya Begum's role as a close advisor to Akbar highlights their political significance. Maham Anga's de facto regency during Akbar's early reign exemplifies the power and authority that women could wield in the political sphere. Nur Jahan's unprecedented authority, including her issuance of royal decrees and involvement in state affairs, marks her as one of the most powerful women in Mughal history. Nur Jahan was a powerful woman who even had her portrait on coins. Mumtaz Mahal's patronage of architecture and her inspiration for the Taj Mahal left a lasting cultural legacy. Meanwhile, Jahanara Begum's patronage of the arts and her influential role in the royal court further demonstrate the critical roles these women played. The power of some Mughal women was so much that they owned ships and different valuable assets.

Connecting this historical context to a specific study, this paper aimed to uncover how Mughal women, particularly queens and empresses, managed the wealth generated through commerce in medieval Mughal India. The findings reveal that these women were active participants in the creation and management of wealth, rather than merely passive recipients. Empress Nur Jahan is renowned for her broad participation in trade and business, managing enormous economic ventures that included precious stones and textiles. Her economic influence allowed her to significantly challenge the patriarchal systems entrenched in the Mughal court. These findings align with new research highlighting the agency of royal women in pre-modern Islamic societies. The study underscores the importance of female economic power throughout the Mughal Empire, demonstrating that women like Jahanara Begum played significant roles in decision-making and policy influence. Jahanara, for instance, was pivotal in decision-making and sought to steer her husband away from harmful habits such as drugs and alcohol (Lal, 2005).

Despite the study's reliance on historical documents, which might be biased or inaccurate, and its focus on prominent individuals, it calls for broader acknowledgment of women's impact. Future research should explore the economic roles of non-royal women in Mughal society, using multidisciplinary methods that combine gender studies, archaeology, and economic history to provide a more comprehensive picture of gender and economy during the Mughal era. This approach will further illuminate the complex roles of women in the Mughal economy and their significant contributions to the empire's prosperity and cultural richness.

These women's active involvement in governance, commerce, and cultural patronage not only emphasizes their importance but also challenges traditionally male-centric historical narratives. The study highlights how these royal women were able to exert substantial influence over state policy and diplomatic relations by controlling the wealth generated through commerce. Their economic independence challenged traditional gender norms and produced role models for women in leadership. This control over wealth and resources had a profound impact on gender dynamics within the empire, showcasing the essential role of women in shaping the Mughal Empire's history (Lal, 1995).

The legacies of Mughal queens and princesses highlight the critical contributions of women in the socio-economic and cultural spheres of the Mughal Empire. Their active participation in various domains not only enriched the empire but also challenged the conventional patriarchal narratives of history. Future studies must delve deeper into the roles of less prominent women to paint a fuller picture of the Mughal society's gender dynamics. By embracing a multidisciplinary approach, we

can better understand the significant and multifaceted roles women played in the Mughal economy and beyond (Moosvi, 1987).

This research can be deemed very important for the current period where we live. Women are still not recognized as much as men due to the prevailing patriarchal mindset. Even though men have always received a more active voice and focus on history, it is crucial to highlight the underrated role of women in the maintenance of one of the biggest empires ever, the Mughal empire. By mentioning the ongoing disparities and challenging traditional mindsets, this study pushes for a more equitable recognition of women's contributions across all spheres. Addressing these issues is essential for fostering a more inclusive and balanced world altogether.

3. CONCLUSION:

In summary, Mughal women were integral to the socioeconomic structure and cultural diversity of the Mughal Empire. In the royal household, queens and princesses such as Gulbadan Begum, Mumtaz Mahal, Jahanara Begum, Ruqaiya Begum, Maryam Zamani, Nur Jahan, and Maham Anga⁴ were not just role models. As a substitute, they played a major role in patronage, commerce, and administration, greatly influencing the empire's economic activities, policies, and creative heritage. As a matter of fact, Mughal women created the world-famous shopping hub, Chandni Chowk in New Delhi. According to an assessment by Jones Lang LaSalle Inc (JLL), Chandni Chowk Bazar receives traction between 4 and 6 lakh people per day, which is more than all of the main malls in Delhi-NCR put together, and a good portion of those visitors would be foreigners visiting the country. (ToI, 2022)

Their ability to question and reinterpret the patriarchal systems of their day is demonstrated by their active participation in commercial and governmental endeavors. These women demonstrated agency and leadership by overseeing massive commercial businesses and influencing official policy, which enhanced the wealth and cultural diversity of the empire. The results of this study emphasize the need to recognize the significant contributions made by Mughal women and advocate for a reevaluation of historically male-centric narratives. Future studies should use multidisciplinary approaches to broaden their coverage and examine the contributions of lesser-known women in order to present a more complete picture of gender dynamics throughout the Mughal era.

Their stories not only enrich our understanding of the Mughal Empire but also underscore the significance of women's contributions to historical progress and societal development. By

recognizing and celebrating the achievements of these influential women, we gain a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the past, paving the way for a more inclusive historical narrative that acknowledges the vital contributions of women across all eras and cultures.

REFERENCES

- Forty Two Decadent Facts About Mumtaz Mahal, The Inspiration For The Taj Mahal. [online] Factinate. Available at: <https://www.factinate.com/people/42-monumental-facts-mumtaz-mahal-inspiration-taj-mahal/>.
- ToI (2024). 9 most powerful women of the Mughal empire. The Times of India. [online] 15 Mar. Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/etimes/trending/9-most-powerful-women-of-the-mughal-empire/photostory/108522986.cms>
- Aggarwal, S. (2023). Jodha Bai Begum: The Enigmatic Rajput Queen of Mughal India. [online] Medium. Available at: <https://medium.com/@shrutiaggarwal01/jodha-bai-begum-the-enigmatic-rajput-queen-of-mughal-india-9a31bad44d7f>
- Agrawal, S. (2018). Nur Jahan, the empress who wielded power in the Mughal court and hunted tigers. [online] ThePrint. Available at: <https://theprint.in/feature/nur-jahan-the-empress-who-wielded-power-in-the-mughal-court-and-hunted-tigers/164869/>.
- Akhtar, S. (2023). Delhi's neglected Roshanara Bagh falls into obscurity. [online] Hindustan Times. Available at: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/delhi-news/delhis-neglected-roshanara-bagh-falls-into-obscurity-101696185484631.html>
- Anon, (n.d.). Maryam Zamani – Still an enigma. [online] Available at: <https://historicalleys.blogspot.com/2018/08/maryam-zamani-still-enigma.html>.
- Author, G. (2020). Roshanara Begum: A Princess or a Powerhouse? [online] The Womb. Available at: <https://www.thewomb.in/roshanara-begum-a-princess-or-a-powerhouse/>
- Bajaj, V. (2018). Mughal Men Ruled South Asia — and One Man Was Ruled by a Woman. The New York Times. [online] 10 Aug. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/08/10/books/review/empress-nur-jahan-ruby-lal.html>.
- BBC (2024). Gulbadan Begum: The epic voyage of a daring Mughal princess. www.bbc.com. [online] 16 Feb. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-68302765>.

- Daily footfall in Chandni Chowk Bazar more than total footfall of major Malls in Delhi NCR: Report. (2022). The Times of India. [online] 29 Jun. Available at: <https://shorturl.at/IO72s>
- De, S. (2020). Rebel princess: Zeb-un-Nissa of the Mughal ménage. [online] The Sunday Guardian Live. Available at: <https://sundayguardianlive.com/lifestyle/rebel-princess-zeb-un-nissa-mughal-menage>
- Desk, I.T.N. and News, I.T. (2024). Roshanara Bagh: Who was Roshanara Begum? Know all about Aurangzeb’s beloved sister and icon of Mughal era. [online] www.indiatvnews.com. Available at: <https://www.indiatvnews.com/trending/offbeat/roshanara-bagh-who-was-roshanara-begum-know-all-about-aurangzeb-s-beloved-sister-and-icon-of-mughal-era-2024-03-21-922583>
- enrouteI (2024). How Mughal women were superb in business? [online] Enroute Indian History. Available at: <https://enrouteindianhistory.com/how-mughal-women-were-superb-in-business/>.
- Findly, E. B., The Capture of Maryam-uz-Zamānī’s Ship: Mughal Women and European Traders. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 108(2), 1988, pp 227- 235.
- Ganeriwal, Y. (2020). The Unconventional Life of Jahanara: A Forgotten Mughal Princess. [online] PRATHA. Available at: <https://www.prathaculturalschool.com/post/jahanara>.
- Ghosh, B. (2021). Maham Anga: The Woman who Called the Shots in Akbar’s Court. [online] PeepulTree. Available at: <https://www.peepulTree.world/livehistoryindia/story/people/maham-anga>
- Google Arts & Culture. (n.d.). Jahanara Begum. [online] Available at: <https://artsandculture.google.com/entity/jahanara-begum/m0207s3?hl=en>
- Google Arts & Culture. (n.d.). Nur Jahan. [online] Available at: <https://artsandculture.google.com/entity/nur-jahan/m02blvy?hl=en>.
- Guchhait, S. and Kaur, D. (2023). Regal Mughal Women: The Veiled Traders. [online] 11, pp.2320–2882. Available at: <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT23A4112.pdf>.
- India Today. (n.d.). Jodha Bai’s 474th birth anniversary: 17 facts about the Queen Mother. [online] Available at: <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/gk-current-affairs/story/jodha-bai-344257-2016-10-01>.
- Ira Mukhtoy, *Daughters of the Sun: Empresses, Queens and Begums of the Mughal Empire*, Aleph Book Company, New Delhi, 2018, p 142
- Jabr, F. (2021). John A. Long - Publications List. [Publicationslist.org](http://publicationslist.org), [online] 14(6). Available at: <http://publicationslist.org/jlong>.

- Kapadia, A. (n.d.). We know all about warrior queens like Lakshambai. Now, let's talk of medieval India's businesswomen. [online] Scroll.in. Available at: <https://scroll.in/article/955106/we-know-all-about-warrior-queens-like-lakshambai-now-let-s-talk-of-medieval-india-s-businesswomen>.
- Khān, 'Ināyat (1990). The Shah Jahan Nama of 'Inayat Khan: An Abridged History of the Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan, Compiled by His Royal Librarian : the Nineteenth-century Manuscript Translation of A.R. Fuller (British Library, Add. 30,777). [online] Google Books. Oxford University Press. Available at: https://books.google.co.in/books?id=n_BtAAAAMAAJ&q=mumtaz+mahal+17+june+1631&redir_esc=y
- Lab, T.H. (2019). Hamida Banu Begum : Akbar's mother was a collector of books! | #TheseMughalWomen. [online] The Heritage Lab. Available at: <https://www.theheritagelab.in/hamida-banu-begum-books/>
- Lal, R. (1995) 'Women and the Economy of Mughal India', Economic and Political Weekly, 30(42), pp. 2677–2684. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4403332> (Accessed: 29 June 2024).
- Lal, R. (2024). The Itinerant Princess Who Chronicled Akbar's Mughal Empire. [online] Atlas Obscura. Available at: <https://www.atlasobscura.com/articles/mughal-princess-gulbadan-begum-author>.
- Lal, Ruby. (ed.) (2013) *Women in Mughal India: Power, Influence, and Social Status*. Oxford University Press.
- Liddle, M. (2024). The unique memoirs of Mughal princess Gulbadan Begum. [online] Frontline. Available at: <https://frontline.thehindu.com/books/review-vagabond-princess-ruby-lal-madhulika-liddle/article68082550.ece>.
- Malhotra, S. (2018). Gulbadan Banu Begum: Mughal Historian & Author Of Humayun-Nama | #IndianWomenInHistory. [online] Feminism in India. Available at: <https://feminisminindia.com/2018/01/25/gulbadan-banu-begum-womens-history/>.
- Moosvi, S. (1987) The Economy of the Mughal Empire c. 1595: A Statistical Study. Oxford University Press.
- Mughallibrary.com. (2015). Available at: <https://www.mughallibrary.com/images-1/jahanara-begum%2C-1635>.
- nadeemrezavi (2021). Akbar's Initial Years: 1560-62 'Petticoat Government'? [online] ASHA: Blast From The Past. Available at:

<https://rezavisblastfromthepast.co.in/2021/04/01/akbars-initial-years-1560-62-petticoat-goverment/>.

pantheon.world. (n.d.). Ruqaiya Sultan Begum Biography | Pantheon. [online] Available at: https://pantheon.world/profile/person/Ruqaiya_Sultan_Begum

Ruby Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World* (Cambridge Studies in Islamic Civilization. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005), p 215.

Sasidharan, D. (2024). Meet Princess Gulbadan, the only woman historian of the Mughal Empire. [online] Vogue India. Available at: <https://www.vogue.in/content/meet-princess-gulbadan-the-only-woman-historian-of-the-mughal-empire>.

Schuster, M. (2017). 'Light of the World:' The Life and Legacy of Nur Jahan. *Armstrong Undergraduate Journal of History*, 7(2). doi:<https://doi.org/10.20429/auj.2017.070203>.

Sen, S. (2022) 'Political economy of gender in India: A critical reappraisal', *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 24(1). Available at: <https://vc.bridgew.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3125&context=jiws>

Sharma, P. (2023). *Unveiling Zeb-un-Nissa : A Historical And Literary Exploration*. © 2023 IJNRD |, [online] 8(8), p.610. Available at: <https://ijnrd.org/papers/IJNRD2308283.pdf>.

SINHA, N. (2020). Who Is (Not) a Servant, Anyway? Domestic servants and service in early colonial India*. *Modern Asian Studies*, pp.1–55. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0026749x19000271>.

Storytrails (2022). *Humayun and Hamida: Love in Time of War*. [online] Storytrails. Available at: <https://storytrails.in/history/humayun-and-hamida-love-in-time-of-war/>.

Sundus, A. (2018). *Zaib-un-Nissa: The Gifted Mughal Princess* | #IndianWomenInHistory. [online] Feminism in India. Available at: <https://feminisminindia.com/2018/10/19/zaib-un-nissa-princess/>

The Asian Age. (n.d.). *Hamida Banu Begum* | The Asian Age Online, Bangladesh. [online] Available at: <https://dailyasianage.com/news/82903/hamida-banu-begum>.

The Heritage Lab. (n.d.). *Ruqaiya Sultan Begum, Author* at The Heritage Lab. [online] Available at: <https://www.theheritagelab.in/author/ruqaiyabegum/>

ThePrint. (2019). She was the first woman builder in Mughal rule and gave Delhi Humayun's Tomb. [online] Available at: <https://theprint.in/pageturner/excerpt/first-woman-builder-in-mughal-rule-who-gave-delhi-humayuns-tomb/327121/>

thewire.in. (n.d.). The Woman Whose Downfall Nearly Killed Akbar. [online] Available at:
<https://m.thewire.in/article/history/mughal-emperor-akbar-maham-anga-assassination-attempt>

UNESCO World Heritage Centre (2010). Taj Mahal. [online] Unesco.org. Available at:
<https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/252/>.

Who was Jodha Bai? (n.d.). The Times of India. [online] Available at:
<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/positivity/who-was-jodha-bai-33334/>.

WISE Muslim Women. (2010). Maham Anga. [online] Available at:
<https://www.wisemuslimwomen.org/muslim-woman/maham-anga-4/>

www.taj mahal.gov.in. (n.d.). Empress MUMTAZ MAHAL. [online] Available at:
<https://www.tajmahal.gov.in/about-mumtaz-mahal.aspx>.

Zeidan, A. (2019). Mumtaz Mahal | Facts, History, Tomb, & Biography | Britannica. In:
Encyclopædia Britannica. [online] Available at:
<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Mumtaz-Mahal>.